

ICLC 2024 - Proposal for Live Performances

1. General Information

- **Performance Title:** Coloring Code - Live Drawing and Coding
- **Main Contact:** Leon Volbers, levoxtrip@gmail.com
- **Additional Performers:** Beverley Anne Edwards
- **Performance Type:** Algorave

2. Abstract

LXT and Beverley Edwards' "The Groovy Hearts Club" is a joyful and vibrant exploration of the interplay between illustration and coding as a live performance medium. In the collaborative performance, the illustrator draws the source images on an iPad, while the live coder transforms these drawings into ever-evolving visual pattern and kaleidoscope of color and fun. This real-time manipulation of the illustrations highlights the expressive potential of both coding and illustration and showcases the improvisational nature of both coding and illustration, emphasizing the ability of both mediums to respond to and react to the creative impulses of the performers.

"The Groovy Hearts Club" invites spectators to experience a unique feedback loop, where each generated image sparks a dynamic response in code, resulting in a continuously evolving visual narrative of excitement and imagination.

3. Video and/or Audio Material

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=uWlxE6VPc8g>

4. Program Note

LXT and Beverley Edwards' "Groovy Hearts Club" is a playful and vibrant live performance that delves into the dynamic interplay between digital illustration and live coding. Creating a kaleidoscope of color and joy, it resembles an improvisational dance between the two mediums. The performance unfolds as the illustrator creates colorful and entertaining images, while the live coder transforms these drawings into mesmerizing visual patterns using the p5live programming environment.

5. Artist(s) Biography

LXT is a creative technologist and visual artist from Germany. His primary focus centers around the intersection of technology and art, utilizing digital media to create new and innovative forms of expression. Marked by an experimental approach and raw imagery, his artistic endeavors aim to unveil novel perspectives and prompt contemplation. Exploring themes such as the relationship between humans and technology, his work ventures into the boundaries of human-machine interaction and the evolving nature of digital connections. Fueled by a passion for the creative exploration of technology and art, he wants to construct novel connections between the digital realm and human experience.

Beverley Edwards is an artist from London, England. She studied Illustration at Norwich University of the Arts in 2013. After graduating, she relocated to Berlin, where she continued working on various kinds of media, including digital art, animation, and street art. She now lives in Barcelona, where she has been expanding her artistic practice by working with ceramics and sculpture.